

Structural characterization of C-S-H gel through an improved deconvolution analysis of NMR spectra

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The structure of the C-S-H gel in hydrated cement samples prepared with and without the addition of silica nanoparticles is studied in this work through the deconvolution of ^{29}Si MAS-NMR spectra. X-ray diffraction and energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis are also considered for the analysis. A method with improved sensitivity and reliability is proposed for the deconvolution of the spectra into elementary components involving a good fitting of both the spectral curve and its second derivative. The increased sensitivity of the deconvolution proves to be especially interesting for the characterization of low concentration components in the NMR spectra, and the high reliability allows properly defining the effect of nanosilica addition on the C-S-H gel nanostructure. In fact, the addition of nanosilica is found to produce a pozzolanic reaction that results in an increase of the mean silicate chain length and an enhancement of the aluminum incorporation into the C-S-H gel phase.

Introduction

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) is a widely used technique for the characterization of cementitious materials. During the last decades, several authors have devoted their efforts to study the behavior of both anhydrous and hydrated cements through this technique and the important changes observed in the spectra upon hydration have been useful to follow the formation of new hydrated phases, especially the C-S-H gel [1–13]. For the case of ^{29}Si MAS-NMR spectra, it is known that the chemical shift is controlled primarily by the nearest-neighbor atomic coordination, but there are also significant next-nearest-neighbor effects, so the spectra are sensitive to tetrahedra polymerization in the gel chains, to geometrical factors such as Si–O bond length or Si–O–Si bond angle, and also to the presence of aluminum atoms in silicon sites.

Deconvolution of spectral curves into their components has been successfully applied to results of NMR spectroscopy to obtain quantitative data on the relative concentration of silicon in different tetrahedral environments and values of the mean chain length (MCL) in C-S-H gels with different values of CaO/SiO₂ ratio and in C-A-S-H gels [3–12]. Nevertheless, when this kind of analysis is performed, it is usual to find that subtle details of the spectral profile are poorly reproduced in the fitting result. Moreover, usually a similarly good fitting of the experimental spectrum may be obtained with a different election of the components and, consequently, different conclusions on the structural properties of the same sample. In this sense, a more sensitive analysis and criteria to determine the most reliable solution would be very valuable.

An advanced characterization of the C-S-H gel structure in hydrated cement samples prepared with and without the addition of silica nanoparticles is presented in this work. A deconvolution method is proposed to provide a high reliability and high sensitivity analysis of the ^{29}Si MAS-NMR spectra of the considered samples. The high sensitivity proves to be especially interesting for the characterization of low concentration components in the NMR data and the high reliability allows properly defining the effect of nanosilica addition on the C-S-H gel nanostructure. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and SEM–EDX have also been used to provide complementary information.

Experimental

Sample preparation and measurement

Three samples were considered in this study: the samples denoted by L100-18 and L100-6 were prepared at a water–cement ratio of 0.4, using a CEM I 52.5R type Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) with an 18 % and a 6 % by weight of cement, respectively, of commercial silica nanoparticles. The nanosilica is presented as a colloidal dispersion and its main properties are a specific surface area of 100 m²/g, a particle size of 30 nm, a pH of 10, and a SiO₂ content of 45 % by weight. The water contained in the colloidal dispersion was considered for the calculation of the total water content of the paste and the amounts of nanosilica addition correspond to the dry weight of the nanoparticles. Samples were cast into 1 × 1 × 6 cm³ prisms using steel molds, where they stayed for 24 h in a chamber at 20 °C and 100 % humidity. After that time,

they were unmolded and introduced in a lime saturated solution at room temperature for the remaining 27 days of curing. The sample denoted by L100-0 was prepared in the same way, but without nanosilica addition and is considered as the reference to analyze the effect of the addition.

X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples were recorded on a Philips PW 1730 diffractometer making use of a graphite monochromator and Cu K α 1 radiation.

The positions occupied by the ^{29}Si atoms were studied by solid nuclear magnetic resonance (MAS-NMR) technique, using a Bruker DSX-300 spectrometer operating at 59.633 MHz and with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the external standard. The experiments were conducted at a room temperature of 21.5 °C, using 90° pulses of 6.0 μs , with a recovery time of 30 s between pulses.

The compositional analysis of the C-S-H gel was performed through energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis implemented in a Hitachi S-4800 scanning electron microscope (SEM-EDX) operated at 20 kV in backscattered electron mode. The samples were embedded in an epoxy resin and polished, in order to improve precision of the quantitative analysis.

Deconvolution method

The deconvolution of the NMR spectra into their elementary components was carried out using Microcalc Origin software and considering the fitting of the spectral profile, as well as the fitting of its second derivative.

In general, NMR spectra are found to be described in the literature by Lorentzian or Gaussian functions or by Voigt functions with partial contributions from both of them. As described in Ref. [2], the shape of the resonance line in NMR spectra (frequency domain) is related to the time function defining the decay rate of the transverse magnetization (free induction decay, FID, in the time domain). A dephasing of the coherent superposition of transverse magnetization occurs due to spin interactions; in liquids and adsorbate systems, these interactions are averaged by the effects like molecular reorientation, diffusion or chemical exchange. In this case, the time function for the FID has an exponential dependence and the resonance lines can be described by a Lorentzian function. On the contrary, for the case of solids, in which the relative orientation and positions of the interacting species do not change with time, there is no efficient averaging of the spin interaction. The FID signal is then given by a more complicated time function that can often be approximated by a Gaussian function. Consequently, a Gaussian line-shape is expected in this case. Taking this into account, a Gaussian profile has been considered for the components in the deconvolution analysis of the NMR spectra in this work, in good agreement with recent references in the literature [5, 9].

The second derivative of a spectrum has interesting properties for the deconvolution analysis [14], which are illustrated by the curves contained in Fig. 1. Each graph depicts two Gaussian peaks of the same height and different widths, together with the curve obtained as their sum. The second derivative of the sum is also shown in each case. The separation between the center value of the Gaussians decreases from Fig. 1a, where the two peaks are completely separated, to Fig. 1c where they are clearly overlapping.

It can be clearly seen from this figure that each second derivative has a minimum at the same wavelength as the underlying peak maximum. Consequently, for the case of a spectral curve formed by the convolution of several Gaussian peaks, the position of the minima in the second derivative can be considered to determine the center position of the components. It can also be observed in Fig. 1c that, in the case of overlapping components, the derivative presents a better resolution to distinguish the components than the initial sum curve. Moreover, the magnitude of the second derivative in each minimum is directly related to the peak width, with a deeper minimum in the case of the sharper peak.

Nevertheless, the second derivative has also some negative properties for its use in the deconvolution analysis [14]. First of all, it can be noted from Fig. 1 that each maximum in the spectral curve gives rise to a minimum and two maxima in the second derivative, so that in complicated spectra it can sometimes be difficult to distinguish true spectral features from the artifacts created by the second derivative calculation. This is the case of the shoulder highlighted by a circle in the second derivative curve of Fig. 1b. Finally, it can be seen that the magnitude of the second derivative is much smaller than that of the original curve. Therefore, in the case of real experimental data, an important degradation of the signal-to-noise ratio would be encountered in the derivative curve that may complicate the minima detection.

In the deconvolution analysis performed in this work, the minima clearly resolved in the second derivative of the spectral curve were considered to define the initial number and position of the Gaussian components. The number of components, as well as their respective positions and widths, were optimized with Non-Linear Fitting procedure included in Microcalc Origin software, in which the merit parameter χ^2 is minimized. This parameter includes the sum of the squares of the deviations of the theoretical curve (calculated as the sum of the Gaussian components) from the experimental curve for a range of chemical shift values. Using this procedure, an excellent fitting of the experimental spectrum was obtained as a sum of Gaussian components for all the spectral curves.

Nevertheless, it is well known that for a given spectral curve, several deconvolution results may be obtained which mathematically reproduce the curve, but with different relative contribution of the components. The critical question is then how to distinguish the right solution among the different fittings that can be obtained from the software. The criterion considered in this work, which is the key point of the analysis, is that not only a good fitting of the spectral profile was required, but also a good fitting of its second derivative. Consequently, the second derivative of the theoretical curve was calculated and compared to the experimental derivative and only when a good fitting of both curves was obtained was the deconvolution solution considered as valid. Nevertheless, within this work the obtained solution was subsequently contrasted with the information acquired by other techniques in order to credit it as correct. This method was proposed by Kucherov and Kochubei [15] for the deconvolution of strongly overlapping bands in infrared absorption spectra and has been successfully used by the authors for the study of structural changes in amorphous SiO thin films [16]. Nevertheless, up to the authors' knowledge, it has not been used before for the analysis of NMR spectra.

Results and discussion

X-ray diffraction patterns

The typical diffractogram of a 28 days hydrated Portland cement paste [17] was obtained for the three studied samples. Figure 2 shows the curves in the range of 2θ from 27.5° to 33.5° in which the main differences observed between the three samples are more evident. The curves show the presence of the anhydrous silicate phases, alite ($\text{Ca}_3\text{SiO}_5\text{-A}$) and belite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{SiO}_4\text{-B}$), and calcite ($\text{CaCO}_3\text{-C}$) is also present due to carbonation of the cement and probably also of the hydrated samples. An important difference is observed in the peak corresponding to portlandite [$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-P}$] at 28.7° , which has a significant signal for samples L100-0 and L100-6, but is practically absent in the diffractogram of L100-18.

The peak at 29.4° has contributions from calcite and alite, but also from the calcium silicate hydrate phase usually observed upon hydration of Ordinary Portland Cements ($1.5\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2\cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}\text{-G}$). In the curve corresponding to L100-18, this peak is broader and slightly shifted to higher angular values due to an additional contribution from another calcium silicate hydrate of formula $\text{Ca}_2\text{SiO}_4\cdot 0.30\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (g in Fig. 2). This phase is consistent with the phases reported in the literature as a result of the hydration of materials with $\text{Ca}/\text{Si} = 2$ [18]. Finally, the broad halo on the base of this peak in the diffractogram of the sample L100-18 is due to the quasi-amorphous character of the C-S-H gel phases.

^{29}Si MAS-NMR spectra deconvolution

The ^{29}Si MAS-NMR spectra after 28 days of hydration of the samples L100-0, L100-6 and L100-18 are shown in Fig. 3, where each curve has been normalized to its maximum value in order to obtain comparable data between the samples.

The three spectra show clearly resolved resonances positioned at chemical shifts (δ) around -71 , -79 and -84 ppm, but important differences are observed in the intensity of these three main peaks as well as in the shape of the curves between them.

The deconvolution of the curves depicted in Fig. 3 into elementary components was performed in order to get a deeper insight into the structural modifications that might be responsible for the observed spectral changes. The procedure described in "Deconvolution method" section was applied to the analysis of each spectrum.

As an example, Fig. 4a shows the second derivative of the NMR spectrum corresponding to sample L100-18. Up to thirteen clear minima are observed in the curve, as indicated by the dotted vertical lines. Additionally, there are some features (marked by circles in Fig. 4a) that might be minima corresponding to overlap components or artifacts from the second derivative calculation as described in “Deconvolution method” section. Initially, only the thirteen components centered at the positions corresponding to the clear minima in Fig. 4a were assumed, in order to consider the minimum number of components. As can be seen in Fig. 4b, these initial center positions are coherent with the shape of the spectral profile.

It is important to note that the noise level of the original spectrum must be low enough to give rise to a smooth second derivative curve as the one shown in Fig. 4a. Otherwise, the detection of the positions of the minima, and consequently, the selection of the initial number and position of the Gaussian components, would not be reliable.

The Non-Linear Fitting procedure was performed avoiding negative values for the Gaussians’ areas and also extremely high values of Gaussians’ widths. The obtained results are depicted in Fig. 5. A final deconvolution into ten components was found to give rise to a calculated curve almost identical to the experimental spectrum (Fig. 5a), coherently with the low value of the final χ^2 merit parameter (2×10^{-5}).

Nevertheless, analyzing the curves in Fig. 5b, it becomes clear that a better fitting may be obtained between the experimental and the calculated second derivatives. First, the calculated curve does not reproduce the experimental one beyond the interval from -65 to -90 ppm, although this is a minor problem since it corresponds to the range with very low signal in the spectrum tails. More important is that the minima in the experimental second derivative are clearly deeper than in the calculated one, even though their positions are perfectly reproduced. Finally, the most significant difference between the two curves is that in the interval from -73 to -77 ppm, highlighted in the figure, where three clear minima are observed in the experimental second derivative and only two wide shoulders in the calculated one. Once again, a high signal-to-noise ratio is mandatory in the second derivative curve in order to reliably identify the differences between the experimental and the calculated curve.

The preliminary result of Fig. 5 was taken as starting point for the improvement of the deconvolution analysis, with an additional component incorporated in the range from -73 to -77 ppm, as suggested by the second derivative analysis. The fitting procedure was performed, and in this case, a tight control of the Gaussian components’ width was mandatory in order to obtain a good fitting of the experimental derivative.

The final deconvolution results for sample L100-18 are collected in Fig. 6a for the spectral curves and Fig. 6b for the second derivatives. A better fitting of the experimental derivative is evident with respect to the curves shown in Fig. 5b in the range corresponding to the tails of the spectrum and also in the values at the minima. Nevertheless, the most interesting improvement is observed in the range from -73 to -77 ppm, where an excellent fitting was obtained in this case.

The same procedure was performed for the deconvolution of the NMR spectra of samples L100-0 and L100-6 and the corresponding results are collected in Fig. 7a, b, respectively. In both cases, the experimental curve is hardly distinguished from the calculated one, and the graphs in the insets show the good agreement between the second derivative of the experimental and calculated spectra. It is important to notice that at chemical shifts between -82.6 and -86.8 ppm, a sharp and deep minimum is observed in the second derivative of the spectra corresponding to the samples with nanosilica addition. On the contrary, in the case of the sample L100-0, a broader and less intense minimum with the main peak at -84.2 ppm and a shoulder at -85.8 ppm is observed in the second derivative curve (highlighted by a dashed rectangle in the inset of Fig. 7a). The fact that the two minima are not well resolved may cause some uncertainty in the results obtained through the deconvolution analysis in this particular range.

In all the three spectra studied, the analysis of the second derivative curves allowed for a better fitting of the spectral curve and, more significantly, to an increase in the reliability of the deconvolution results. The key to claim for this increased reliability is the fact that several configurations were found to give a good fitting of each experimental spectrum, with similar values of the χ^2 parameter, but the components depicted in Figs. 6 and 7 were the only configurations found to give a good fitting of the corresponding second derivative as well.

The relative area of the Gaussian components as obtained from the analysis of ^{29}Si NMR spectra of the samples are compared in Fig. 8, in the range from -65 to -89 ppm, corresponding to values of relative area higher than 1.0 %. Apart from the expected components centered at around -71.1 , -78.8 , and -84 ppm, several intermediate components are obtained that determine the spectral shapes. Table 1 includes the displacement values of every component, together with their corresponding relative areas. Interesting differences are observed between the three samples, especially between the sample L100-0 and the two samples with nanosilica addition.

Energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis

An elemental analysis of the gel phase in sample L100-18 was performed by SEM–EDX. A similar analysis was precluded in the case of samples L100-0 and L100-6 as a high morphological inhomogeneity was observed in their surfaces and it was not possible to reliably identify homogeneous areas for the analysis of the C-S-H phase. For the L100-18 sample, up to 33 spectra were recorded, corresponding to seven different zones throughout the sample surface. Figure 9a shows the general morphology observed, while the images in Fig. 9b, c show in more detail the areas where the EDX spectra were obtained.

In spite of the inherent low resolution of the SEM–EDX analysis that makes it difficult to avoid the presence of phases different from C-S-H gel in the analyzed volume, useful estimations may be obtained for the mean composition of the gel phase. The values of Al/Si ratio obtained for all the 33 points considered in the analysis provided a mean Al/Si ratio equal to 0.12 with a low dispersion (standard deviation of 0.03). Moreover, a mean value of Ca/Si in the sample L100-18 equal to 1.9 (standard deviation of 0.2) was obtained, which is coherent with those reported in the literature [19].

Discussion

For the interpretation of the NMR spectra, the widely accepted dreierkette-based model for the structure of C-S-H gel [3] has been considered. Within this model, the gel is formed by silicate chains with a dreierkette structure, in which SiO_4 tetrahedra repeat themselves at intervals of three units and the chains have a finite length following the $3n - 1$ rule with $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ for the number of tetrahedra. Different environments of silicon are denoted by Q_n ($0 \leq n \leq 4$), where Q is a silicate tetrahedron and n is the number of oxygen atoms which bridge to adjacent tetrahedra. The model also considers the possibility of Al^{3+} incorporation into the C-S-H gel chains, substituting Si^{4+} in bridging or in paired tetrahedra. In such case, the aforementioned notation is generally replaced by $\text{Q}_n(\text{rAl})$ to represent a silicate tetrahedron, Q, connected via oxygen bridges to r aluminum and to $n - r$ silicon atoms ($0 \leq n \leq 4$ and $0 \leq r \leq n$).

Taking this model into account, the main peaks observed in the ^{29}Si NMR spectra of OPC samples have been assigned in the literature to silicon in the different environments [1–13]. Regarding the Q_0 units characteristic of the anhydrous phases, it is known that there are four different C2S conformers and that each of them has just one silicon site in an isolated SiO_4^{4-} tetrahedron (Q_0 site), giving rise to a single resonance at -70.7 ppm (α -C2S), -70.8 ppm (α' -C2S), -71.4 ppm (β -C2S), or -73.5 ppm (γ -C2S) [1]. In the case of C3S phase, seven resolved resonances from -69.0 to -74.7 ppm are attributable to isolated tetrahedra [1, 12]. Considering these data, the Gaussian components of the NMR spectra centered at displacement values between -62.3 and -73.0 ppm (Table 1) may be related to Q_0 units due to traces of crystals from anhydrous phases that remain in the cement, as observed by XRD (see Fig. 2).

Moreover, according to the literature [1–12], the signal observed in ^{29}Si spectra of hydrated OPC samples, centered at around -79.0 may be attributed to Q_1 units in C-S-H gel. This clarifies the assignment of the component centered at -78.8 ppm, which is common for the three samples in Fig. 8, as corresponding to silicon in tetrahedra involved in dimers and chain endings, which share only one oxygen atom with neighboring SiO_4 tetrahedra [$\text{Q}_1(0\text{Al})$].

For the case of silicon in pure Q_2 units, $\text{Q}_2(0\text{Al})$, some authors [1, 3, 7, 8] have reported a single peak in NMR spectra at a displacement value around -85 ppm that may explain the components centered at -84.5 – -84.7 ppm found in this work for samples L100-6 and L100-18. Other authors [4, 9] found an additional peak at -82 – -83 ppm, coherent with our results for L100-0, and associated it to bridging units; nevertheless, this assignment is not fully accepted in the literature [10, 19].

A resonance at around -82 ppm has also been observed and assigned to Q2(1Al) units in several works [3, 7–11, 20, 21] that would explain the peak at $-81.4/-81.7$ ppm obtained for the three samples as depicted in Fig. 8. The peaks centered at $-87.2/-88.5$ ppm might be due to a minor content of Q3 units in the gel [4].

For a further analysis of the results, it is interesting to note the particular behavior of the components in the range from -83 to -86 ppm in Fig. 8. Two components are observed for the sample L100-0, centered at -83.7 and -85.4 ppm, that could be assigned to Q2(0Al) units in bridging and paired positions, respectively. Nevertheless, within this assignment, a higher relative contribution would be attributed to Q2b(0Al) units (of 9.0 %) than to Q2p(0Al) units (of 6.1 %). This behavior is not compatible with the dreierkette-based model for the structure of C-S-H gel, in which the $3n - 1$ rule for the chain length implies that each bridging silicon tetrahedron (Q2b(0Al)) must be connected to two paired tetrahedra and consequently the ratio Q2b/Q2p cannot be higher than 0.5.

Some authors [4] have suggested a deviation of the $3n - 1$ rule by the presence of chains of three tetrahedra in synthetic C-S-H gels with MCL values close to 3. Within this assumption, the Q2b/Q2p ratio higher than 0.5 obtained for the sample L100-0 would be accounted for by trimmers in which the bridging tetrahedra would be connected to chain-ending Q1(0Al) units. Nevertheless, in order to define whether the previous assignment is correct and the results of this work suggest the existence of such trimmers, further analysis and a better resolution in the spectrum of sample L100-0 in this range of chemical shift would be necessary.

On the contrary, for the sample L100-18, only one component is found related to Q2(0Al) units centered in this case at a chemical shift value of -84.7 ppm between the values obtained for the two Q2(0Al) components in the sample L100-0 and corresponding to the sharp and deep minimum observed in the second derivative of the NMR spectrum (Fig. 6b). This single component must include the contribution of both Q2b(0Al) and Q2p(0Al) tetrahedra. The high relative area (20.4 %) of the component associated to Q2(1Al) for this sample suggests that the main part of silicon tetrahedra in bridging position have been replaced by aluminum tetrahedra, so that the relative contribution of Q2b(0Al) units must be low and may not be resolved from the more pronounced peak corresponding to Q2p(0Al) units [4, 10]. A similar behavior is observed for the L100-6 sample, with only one component in this range of chemical shift.

Finally, it is interesting to analyze in detail the components at chemical shifts around $-75.0/-76.8$ ppm, between the range corresponding to anhydrous phases and that corresponding to Q1(0Al) units in C-S-H gel. The reliable detection of these components, related to the minima in the curves of the second derivative that were highlighted in Figs. 5 and 6, is achieved through the improved sensitivity of the deconvolution method proposed in this work.

A ^{29}Si chemical shift of approximately -75 ppm is expected to correspond to Q1(1Al) units [20] that appear upon aluminum substitution for silicon in paired positions. Recent computational simulation studies [22–25] have proven that replacement of Si^{4+} by Al^{3+} is energetically viable in both bridge and paired sites, although the former are preferred. Probably due to this preference, experimental evidence of aluminum at paired sites in C-S-H gel is scarcely found in the literature and is related to the use of improved resolution methods. This is the case of the work by Faucon et al. [26] in which the use of multiple quantum (MQ) MAS-NMR allows the separation of different contributions not resolved in the original ^{27}Al MAS-NMR spectra. Moreover, experimental evidence of aluminum tetrahedra in paired positions is reported in the recent work by Pardal et al. [11] who suggest this type of substitution in C-A-S-H gels with high Ca/Si ratios and subsequently low values of the MCL. Nevertheless, the resonance in this range of chemical shifts may as well be related to Q1(0Al) sites with different chemical shifts due to geometrical effects, like bond length or bond angle variations, in the predominantly amorphous structure of C-S-H gel phase. Both possibilities have been considered in this work.

Figure 10 depicts the relative area corresponding to the different Qn units in the three samples, as obtained from the data collected in Table 1. Figure 10a considers the assignment of the components in the range $-75/-76.8$ ppm to Q1(1Al) units, while Fig. 10b considers the assignment to Q1(0Al). The MCL and the aluminum to silicon ratio (Al/Si) of the C-S-H gel may be calculated from these data using the following equations [3].

$$MCH = \frac{Q^1(0Al) + Q^2(0Al) + \frac{3}{2}(Q^1(1Al) + Q^2(2Al))}{\frac{1}{2}(Q^1(0Al) + Q^1(1Al))} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{Al}{Si} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}(Q^1(1Al) + Q^2(1Al))}{Q^1(0Al) + Q^2(0Al) + Q^1(1Al) + Q^2(1Al)} \quad (2)$$

The values of MCL and Al/Si ratio in the gel phase as obtained from these equations were calculated for the three samples under study considering the two possible assignments for the components in $-75.0/-76.8$ ppm. The results are collected in Table 2, where significant differences are observed between the values of Al/Si obtained within the two options. In the case of sample L100-0, a value of 0.17 is obtained when the existence of Q1(1Al) units is considered, which is twice the value of 0.08 obtained in option b. This latter value is coherent with the Al/Si ratio between 0.05 and 0.10 reported in the literature for C-S-H gel formed by Portland cement hydration in different conditions [8, 10, 21, 27, 28] while the former value of 0.17 is only obtained when alumina-rich additives are considered [7, 10].

For the samples with nanosilica lower differences are encountered between the Al/Si ratios of the two options in Table 2, although in all the cases a higher value is obtained when Q1(1Al) units are considered.

In order to clarify the correct assignment for the components in $-75.0/-76.8$ ppm, the mean value of Al/Si ratio equal to 0.12 obtained by EDX for the sample L100-18 may be considered. This experimental value is significantly lower than the 0.17 value calculated through the deconvolution of ^{29}Si NMR spectrum of this sample when the existence of Q1(1Al) units in the gel was considered. In fact, the Al/Si ratio obtained through SEM-EDX is comparable to the value of 0.14 collected for L100-18 in Table 2 as option b, thus suggesting the suitability of the assignment of the components in the range of $-75/76.8$ ppm in the deconvolution results to Q1(0Al) units.

According to the results shown in Fig. 10b for the L100-0 sample, without nanosilica, the main contribution to the structure is from Q1 units that account for a 43.4 % of the total NMR spectrum. A high contribution of Q0 units of 29.4 %, a similar concentration of Q2 units (27.0 %) and an almost undetectable contribution from Q3 units (0.2 %) are obtained, indicating a low hydration degree that is consistent with the low value of MCL (3.5). These data suggest that the C-S-H gel in this sample would be basically formed by short chains.

Comparing the results for L100-18 and L100-0 samples, an important decrease of the total Q0 and Q1 units concentration (to a 20.6 and 31.0 %, respectively) is observed with the nanosilica addition, while the percentage of Q2 and Q3 units significantly increases up to 44.4 and 4 %, respectively. These variations give rise to an increase of the MCL up to 5.5 in L100-18 and suggest the presence of longer chains in the C-S-H gel. The larger proportion of C-S-H gel in the paste observed by SEM is coherent with the reduction of Q0 and may be responsible for the broad halo observed in the XRD pattern of this sample (Fig. 2). This, altogether with the clear reduction in the portlandite XRD signal, suggests the presence of a pozzolanic reaction and an acceleration of hydration reactions due to the addition of nanosilica, in good agreement with the results of previous works [29–32].

It is also interesting to note the increase of the Al/Si ratio in the gel when nanosilica is added to the cement (Table 2), despite the expected reduction of this ratio in the matrix. In fact, this result is in good agreement with experimental data previously reported [30] which suggest that nanosilica promotes the incorporation of aluminum into the structure of the C-S-H gel in detriment of Al-rich phases like ettringite.

Conclusions

The main conclusions that can be inferred from the present work are the following:

- A method of improved sensitivity and reliability has been proposed for the deconvolution of NMR spectral features into elementary components. The key factor to obtain more reliable results is the requirement of a good fitting of the second derivative of the spectral curve, as well as an excellent fitting of the spectrum itself. Furthermore, a low noise level and a high resolution of the NMR spectrum have been identified as essential factors to obtain reliable results from the quantitative analysis of the results.
- The ^{29}Si MAS-NMR spectra of hydrated OPC samples, with and without the addition of silica nanoparticles, have been analyzed and a reliable assignment of the Gaussian components has been achieved in terms of the dreierketten chain model accepted for the C-S-H structure. Results from SEM-EDX analysis have been necessary to define the more reliable assignment for the components in the chemical shift range between -75.0 and -76.8 ppm.
- For the sample of OPC without silica additions a low hydration degree and consistently a low value of MCL in the C-S-H gel (3.5) have been obtained.

- In the samples with addition of silica nanoparticles a larger proportion of C-S-H gel in the paste, an increase of the MCL and a reduction in the portlandite XRD signal suggest the presence of a pozzolanic reaction and an acceleration of the hydration reactions due to the addition. Moreover, the obtained increase of the Al/Si ratio in the C-S-H gel suggests that nanosilica promotes the incorporation of aluminum into the structure of this phase.

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